

Navigating the Contending Research Paradigms: From Empiricism, Lived Experiences, Identity Politics, to Social Liberation

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ABSTRACT

In the world in which we live, social realities are complex, for which reason researchers face the problem of the way in which to navigate the research landscape in search of the proper lenses with which to investigate social phenomena. The overall purpose of this paper was to lay down systematically the four major paradigms from which researchers can select and use in dissecting, understanding, and explaining a given social matter. The research questions raised, and the corresponding research objectives, included the following: 1) what are the key tenets of the contending research paradigms of positivism, interpretivism, critical theory, and radical engagements for social transformation? 2) How do they compare in reference to methodologies and data gathering? 3) What are the merits and demerits of each paradigm in dealing with social issues? Literature reviewed included the core corpus of seminal and cutting-edge publications of each paradigm. The findings revealed that each research paper has at its core an embedded paradigm with a complex set of profound assumptions about the underlying ontology, change, epistemology, logic, objectivity, and ethics. One research paradigm is not better than the others. Each research paradigm searches for different matters to observe and yields different results. Consequently, researchers are enjoined to ponder about the paradigms they use in the conduct of their research, prior to the commencement of their writing enterprise, as paradigms have grave implications for social research, social outputs, and social outcomes.

Keywords: Interpretivism, Critical Theory, Positivism, Research Paradigms, Social Transformation

Background of the Problem

In the world of research, paradigms are important in guiding the development of perspectives and methods, without which the research process will meander and does not know how to proceed and in which direction.

Problem Statement

The problem is to determine the best paradigm suited for a particular research project. Such a choice affects the ways in which we gather and interpret research data obtained through means, such as fieldwork, literature analysis, surveys, interviews, focus groups, experiments, and other research data collection methods.

Research Gaps

Research paradigms are key in understanding the perspectives from which an author and one's research work emanate. However, most authors scarcely are aware of or comprehend what paradigms of research are, for which this paper was presented.

Purpose of this Paper

The purpose of this article was to expound on the four major sets of contending research paradigms.

Research Questions

This paper answered the following questions:

1. What are the key tenets of the contending research paradigms of positivism, interpretivism, critical theory, and radical engagements for social transformation?
2. How do they compare in reference to methodologies and data gathering?
3. What are the merits and demerits of each paradigm in dealing with social issues?

Objectives of the Study

Based on the foregoing research questions, the objectives this paper were the following:

1. To identify the principal features of the four major sets of paradigms of research;
2. To compare their methodologies and data collection methods; and,
3. To evaluate the benefits and drawbacks of each paradigm

Justification of the Study

This paper on contending research paradigms benefits both academicians and practitioners, as they will cognize the importance of knowing, understanding, selecting, and applying a given paradigm in the conduct of their research.

Contribution of the Paper

This article provided a summary of the major features of each of the four sets of research paradigms, by which authors can ponder upon the perspectives they utilize in the conduct of their research.

Coverage of the Study

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Scope

This paper presented the four major sets of opposing research paradigms. One set investigates the individual level. Another set examines the group level. Two competing sets of opposing research paradigms focus on the macro level of analysis.

Limitation

It identified several paradigms. However, several paradigms are related for several reasons, such as all paradigms that focused on the micro or individual level were put together in one same basket of paradigms. Those paradigms that focused on the group level were also classified under one same set of paradigms. However, while there are two contending sets of paradigms which focus on the macro level of analysis, they differ in their view of the status quo. One macro-level set of paradigms remains at the realm of the status quo, while the other macro-level set of paradigms critique and oppose the status quo as well as promote social change. Thus, they were separated into two contending sets of paradigms. Thus, all paradigms were grouped together in similar sets, yielding a total of four contending paradigms.

Human beings are rational and emotional beings who are not devoid of biases, partiality, or partisanship. Note that each paradigm is complex and has its own set of biases. From the point of view of research and the philosophy of science, all paradigms are co-equal. One paradigm is not better than the other. Rather, they are different. Employing one paradigm over another reveals deep-seated values, attitudes, and preferences, whether by design or inadvertently.

Delimitation

The output of this conceptual and analytic paper is based upon my own analysis and interpretation of the different paradigms, after which I categorized all paradigms cited into four major contending paradigms. Other authors would organize these paradigms differently, which is not the focus of this paper. See Figure 1 below.

Figure 1: Coverage of the Study

LITERATURE REVIEW

This section presented the concepts that guided the conduct of the research of this article. First, the principal concepts of scientific revolution, falsifiability, and paradigm shifts were explained, after which these concepts were operationalized with respect to the manner in which these concepts were utilized in this analytic paper.

Conceptual Definition of Terms

Kuhn and Popper were among the most influential thinkers in the field of the philosophy of science in the twentieth century, both of whom argued that scientific knowledge changes through time and space (Kuhn, 2012; Popper, 2002). Accordingly, science is not static, but is ever shifting, based upon the latest discoveries or results of scientific experiments and observations, for which reason there are scientific revolutions.

For Popper, our understanding of science can move forward when it is falsifiable. For Kuhn, our understanding of science advances when one theory falsifies another. Thomas Kuhn coined the term paradigm (Kuhn, 2012). A paradigm is a conceptual and conceptual model which has its own sets of patterns, which provides one way of viewing social reality. Paradigms are mutually exclusive, as each paradigm has its own set of patterns, which is exclusive to itself. A paradigm provides a set of perspectives or ways in which to view and understand the world. A paradigm provides the tools with which to observe, organize, and understand data of research. Popper perceives science as advancing gradually and cumulatively for the evolution of a normative philosophy of science. Kuhn describes science as moving forward revolutionarily in leaps and bounds.

Operational Definition of Terms

In application of the philosophy of science according to which scientific knowledge is impermanent and changes, this paper argued that there were breaks in knowledge, through falsification of different paradigms, which led to the emergence of four co-equal umbrellas of research paradigms.

For this paper, there are four major sets of contending paradigms, each of which contains several paradigms with different specific elements, yet overall, they share common features, namely:

1. Positivist Paradigm
2. Interpretivist Paradigm
3. Critical Paradigm
4. Transformative Paradigm

This analytic paper filled the gap by providing a systematic review of the major contending research paradigms. Research paradigms provide the philosophical basis upon which research methodology rests.

For the visualization of the four contending research paradigms, see Figure 2 below.

Figure 2: Four Contending Research Paradigms
Source: ©2023 Rey Ty

METHODOLOGY

Research Philosophy

This research is an analytic work which delved into the philosophy of science. It focused on the concepts of scientific revolutions, falsifiability, and paradigm shifts.

Research Design

As a paper that dealt with the philosophy of science, this article is a piece of qualitative research, which investigated the variety of research paradigms.

Research Approach

This work resorted to the deductive research approach, as materials were culled from existing literature.

Research Strategies

Searching seminal work and cutting-edge literature, this article employed the research strategy of archival research. For this reason, this research was resource-intensive with respect to the articles and books reviewed.

Research Data Collection Methods

Data gathered for this paper were based upon archival research of existing literature on matters related to research paradigms. Dissimilar and insightful perspectives from the materials culled from the document search of each source, which enriched the strength of this paper.

Sources of Research Data

The materials used in this article were both journal articles and books. Varied sources of information were used, which offered an extensive span of materials with discrete perspectives. They included both classics and state-of-the-art literature on research paradigms.

Research Data Analysis Methods

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To analyze the different literature that discussed the different research paradigms, this paper utilized document analysis to review existing literature. It also used thematic analysis with a view to detect persistent themes.

Time Horizon

This paper is longitudinal in terms of time coverage, as it investigated the development of ideas of the different paradigms through time. It inspected classic writings as well as explored the latest literature on matters related to research paradigms.

Research Data Interpretation Methods

While engaged in data gathering and reading, qualitative information was coded and categorized in a systematic manner. Upon completion of this analytic paper, a grounded theory is structured thereafter. Data interpretation was likewise presented through data visualization in the form of summary figures that summarized the narrative explanation of the data analysis.

Research Ethics

As this research relied solely on the existing literature, it affected no one and there was no harm. For the summary of the research methodology, see Figure 3 below.

Figure 3: Research Methodology of This Article
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FINDINGS

This paper raised three research questions to which this section provided the responses. Data analysis yielded a product of four major baskets of paradigms of research.

Data Analysis

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Research Question 1

What are the key tenets of the contending research paradigms of positivism, interpretivism, critical theory, and radical engagements for social transformation?

There are four major sets of research paradigms, under which other distinct paradigms with similar tenets were subsumed. They are:

1. Positivist Paradigm
2. Interpretivist Paradigm
3. Critical Paradigm
4. Transformational Paradigm

Positivist Paradigm. Positivism stressed measuring a given phenomenon without value judgment (Comte, 1988). Oftentimes, premium is given to the use of quantification and measurements. This paradigm is a stickler on the use of the scientific method. Positivism gained currency in the natural sciences, such as biology, chemistry, and physics. It is also useful in the applied sciences and technology, such as medicine, nursing, dentistry, chemical engineering, civil engineering, mechanical engineering, structural engineering, and the like. Positivist social sciences underlie the positivist paradigm, such as psychology and sociology for the most part. Professional degrees such as business and economics are heavily positivist. The emphasis of the positivist paradigm is to investigate and describe the status quo as it is, allowing for minor gradual shifts.

Positivism is pervasive in many fields, such as biology, business, computer science, management, engineering, professional fields, quantitative social research, including anthropology, political science, psychology, and sociology. Related paradigms include, among others, behavioral studies, cybernetics and communication theory, decision-making in complex systems, empirical research, structural functionalism, structuralism, functionalism, pragmatism, systems analysis, and systems thinking in management.

Interpretivist Paradigm. Interpretivism deals with making sense of the world, with meaning making, with the comprehension of subjectively interpreted significance (Weber, 1977). Here, context is important and is the point of departure. It gives value to qualitative cognition of social phenomena. This paradigm is used in anthropology, business research, cognitive psychology, education, philosophy, sociology, and other research that treat data qualitatively.

Data is gathered from lived experiences and subjective understanding of the world. The focus is to produce thick description (Geertz, 1973). There are many related paradigms. They include constructivism, contextual analysis, cultural analysis, existentialism, hermeneutics, phenomenology, philosophical investigations, and symbolic interactionism.

Interpretivism is a powerful tool in business to increase profit exponentially. Business and industry use interpretive paradigm to extract the “cool” sub-cultures of the youth. Business researchers identify the coolest young folks in school and in regular settings, such as in the streets and at the malls. They follow these young adults around. They have unique but trendy fashion sense. Big businesses learn about their lifestyles, the clothes they wear, their fashion sense, the colors and designs they use, as well as the ways in which they mix and match their wardrobe and the places they frequent on a regular basis. This qualitative research that focuses on the interpretivist paradigm produces unique ideas for businesses and companies to produce new product lines, which often become hits and lead to earning big bucks for the companies which produce new products based on the fashion sense of the cool kids or the places they

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visit. Some young adults benefit and profit from such interpretivist research. Think of social media influencers: from Paris Hilton and Kim Kardashian to all the copycats today. Many “reality shows” so to speak on television in fact cash in on these trendy individuals and families who also benefit from these business deals.

Paradigms related to interpretivism include, among others, constructivism, existentialism, symbolic interactionism, hermeneutics, and phenomenology.

Critical Paradigm. Critical theory originated in Germany with the Frankfurt School of thought in philosophy (Marcuse, 2007). It concentrates on the critique of society and questions existing social norms and ideological positions. From Germany, critical theory was extended to the study of different societies, not only critique of culture in the abstract, but also critique of specific elements of culture, such as color, gender, ethnicity, nationality, caste, and later environmental practices. Clearly, group rights are important here. Key terms in critical paradigms include culture wars, identity politics, intersectionality, and social justice.

Variants of critical paradigm includes critical legal theory, critical race theory, intersectionality, and more (Crenshaw, 1996; Rancire & Swenson, 2011; Ty et al., 2010). Critical paradigm is widely used in feminist studies, interfaith dialogue in religious studies, philosophy, and sociology. Critical paradigms appear in the business sector in the form of “corporate social responsibility” (CSR) and “environmental and social governance” (ESG). Related paradigms include African American and Black studies, Asian American studies, feminism, gender studies, environmental studies, Latinx studies, Native American studies, postmodernism, post-structuralism, and queer theory.

Transformational Paradigm. The transformational paradigm is one that promotes systemic, structural, and conjunctural social change. History and social context are important elements of this research, not abstract concepts, and ideas. Current events are guideposts which assist in the development of agenda for social transformation. The status, well-being, and empowerment of all working people is a major concentration of this paradigm. The transformational paradigm is utilized in anti-colonialism, economics, education, philosophy, political economy, political philosophy, political science, political theory, sociology, and theology.

Transformative research challenges and opposes the power imbalance, power relations, and the stronghold of the elite over economic, political, and cultural power. It seeks the comprehensive transformation of the structural constraints of society. Transformative research is action oriented, which aims to overturn power inequalities in society. Related paradigms include critique of political economy, mass democratic movement, national liberation, radical engagements for social transformation, liberation theology, social liberation.

Research Question 2

How do the contending research paradigms compare in reference to methodologies and data gathering?

There are implications in the choice and use of a given research paradigm. Each research paradigm is suitable for the application of different research methodologies and data collection methods.

Positivist Paradigm. Research using the positivist paradigm is deductive and oftentimes quantitative. They search for empirical data for description, statistical testing, or experimentation. Positive

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research uses the hypothetico-deductive method. Variables are identified, using involving independent variables and dependent variables, but could also include many other types of variables. For clarity and measurability, concepts must be defined conceptually and operationally. Existing theories are utilized for hypothesis testing.

Research data collection methods include surveys, statistical analysis, or experiments, depending on the requirements of specific research projects. Data analysis is based upon the presentation of numeral data. Descriptive statistics are often laid out in a frequency distribution table (FDT). Inferential statistics are derived from statistical tests of varied types. In the sciences, experiments are the basis upon which data confirm or refute the hypothesis of the study. Positivist studies can examine variables and generalize at the macro-level of analysis, such as voting behavior, views about women's health rights, and attitudes towards war.

Interpretivist Paradigm. If on the one hand positivist research is quantitative, deductive, and value-free, interpretivist research on the other hand is qualitative, inductive, and value-laden. The level of analysis in an interpretivist paradigm is often at the micro-level of analysis, meaning at the individual level, such as individual village, individual office worker, or a small community. Unlike positivist research, the values of individuals carry a lot of weight in interpretivist research.

Research data gathering methods include field visits, exposure to a given milieu, immersion for an extended period in an office setting or a village, and participant observation. Thematic analysis is one way by which data is analyzed.

Critical Paradigm. If positivist research works well on the massive macro-level of analysis and interpretivist research functions well on the micro-level of analysis, critical research operates perfectly well on the meso-level of analysis. Positivism tends to identify variables as sexes (male, female), education (none, primary, secondary, vocational, tertiary, graduate, doctorate), income (unemployed, poor, middle class, and rich). Interpretivist research focuses on the individual: individual person, individual office, and the like. Critical research focuses on the group level of analysis. Under scrutiny are women, gender roles, indigenous people, ethnic minorities, the environment, the religious sector, civil society, and non-governmental organizations.

Data collection methods involve multidisciplinary research, combining insights from different fields of study. Instead of merely reporting on facts and figures as they are, as in positivist research, or reporting on the feelings and meaning making of individuals, as in interpretivist research, critical research champions the rights of groups, such as women's rights, minority rights, LGBTQIA+ rights, and so on. They advocate social justice for groups, not merely treat people as people in the abstract or as simply men or women, the way positivist research does. Critical research emphasizes the need to zero in on the positionality, needs, and demands of groups. If positivism asserts that all human beings have human rights, critical theory asserts that we must struggle for the social justice of groups; hence, critical theorists are often called as social justice warriors (SJW).

Data analysis methods include critical discourse analysis and narrative analysis.

Transformative Paradigm. This transformative paradigm is similar to the positivist paradigm, as both are capable of examining society as a whole at the macro-level of analysis. Their point of commonality

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ends there. Whereas positivist research describes the world as it is, transformative research aims to change the status quo to overhaul the existing system with a view to usher in a new system.

In transformative research, the research methodology is based upon action research (AR). It is change related and is by nature participatory. In this case, the researcher is a scholar-practitioner who is involved in and a partner in social change, not only in words or research, but importantly in deeds. Data collection methods involve community engagement, participatory action research (PAR), as well as community-based participatory action research (CPAR). For more details about the distinctions among the different types of action research, read articles about case studies listed in the references below (Ty, 2021, 2009).

Research Question 3

What are the merits and demerits of each paradigm in dealing with social issues?

Positivist Paradigm. Positivist research projects are accurate. They discuss facts and figures without editorializing. Phenomena are measured precisely. Phenomena are what they are, regardless of how we think or feel. These are the advantages of the positivist paradigm.

The problems with the positivist paradigm are not miniscule. For one, positivist research provides an oversimplified view of social phenomena and the physical world. Abstract numbers are assigned to prove or disprove a hypothesis. However, we all know that human thought, life as such, and the material world are complex. In addition, positivist research concentrates on objectives, eschewing subjectivity. Far from being neutral and value-free, all human beings have subjective preferences and feelings. For this reason, positivist research is somewhat outdated, in which other paradigms can fill the gap.

Interpretivist Paradigm. The beauty of interpretivist research is that it catches detailed insights in each specific context. It provides thick descriptions (Geertz, 1973). Furthermore, it puts subjectivity on a pedestal, which is lacking in positivist paradigm. However, the strength of interpretivist research regarding subjectivity is also its weakness. Too much emphasis is placed on subjectivity, at the expense of objective facts and figures. For instance, if a person says, “the sun in the south” or “moon looks the same every night,” the researcher reports this in interpretivist research. A reader who does not know what interpretivist research will be confused, as I was when I took my first and subsequent anthropology classes. Interpretivist research does not have the duty to correct factual errors, as it only reports on the subjective meanings and feelings that an individual reports in research. Researchers must notify readers what interpretivist research entails so as not to confuse them.

Critical Paradigm. Critical research receives positive marks for advancing social equity and social justice. It promotes the rights of groups which otherwise will go unnoticed. Positive research asserts that “all men are created equal” in the abstract. Critical research, however, questions such a statement on a few counts. Firstly, “men” literally do not include women. Secondly, women factually enjoy less privileges and rights in most society in the whole world today. At least for these two reasons, critical theory raises the question of “where the different groups are when we say ‘all humans’ are equal.” Think of other marginalized groups, such as indigenous peoples, ethnic minorities, religious minorities, linguistic minorities, people of lower social status, and the like.

While critical research rightly makes the invisible visible in research projects, such as the role and status of women in society, some problems arise. Firstly, while taking sides to defend the rights of groups is praiseworthy, there are concerns as to the extent to which such positionality is biased politically and in

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fact hurts another group. Culture wars could break out: for instance, there are debates regarding affirmative action, to which people of different colors have their solid arguments for or against it. Rigorous empirical data is needed, not only for the defense of social justice: a balance must be struck between the two.

Transformative Paradigm. The advancements that transformative research benefit the majority, which is composed of the working people. It investigates the history of societies and the actual social conditions of people in society. Unlike positivist research which merely describes and measures the status quo, transformative research acts for the transformation of systems and structures of society.

However, no matter how magnanimous the call for societal transformation, bringing about social change is not an easy task, much less, a research work can realistically achieve. The call for action to transform society at large is magnanimous, yet its immediate achievability after the conduct of research is unlikely in the short term, barring any unforeseen circumstances.

DISCUSSION

There are both strengths and weaknesses in each research paradigm. One paradigm is not better than the others. The issue is to choose the best research paradigm for a specific purpose for a specific type of research.

Positivist Paradigm. Positivist research draws conclusions based upon numbers and figures. Observation, evidential empirics, and measurements are the foundations upon which interpretations are based. Its objective is to search for and identify trends, correlations, and causality. Precision and replicability are the hallmarks of positivism. However, the Achilles' heels of positivist research lie in the inability to examine complexities and contextual elements of the conditions of humanity.

For examples of the ways in which the four contending paradigms can be used in the business field, see Table 1 below.

Table 1: Application of the Four Contending Research Paradigms in the Different Subfields in Business
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Subfields	Positivism	Interpretivism	Critical Theory	Social Change
Accounting	Auditing practices in China	Qualitative accounting ethics research of a concerned citizen in Sweden	Critical examination of corporate accounting in Chile with a focus on transparency	Community-based accounting for nonprofits in Peru with a focus on accountability
Economics	Econometric modeling in India	Imagining Green Economics in Canada	Critical evaluation of economic inequality in Argentina with a focus on social justice	Community-based economic development in Nigeria with a focus on poverty reduction
Finance	Stock market analysis in Japan	Qualitative studies of a Housewife's financial decision-making in Australia	Analysis of financial market disparities in Germany with a focus on diversity	Sustainable finance initiatives in Mexico with a focus on green investments
Human Resources	Employee surveys in Germany	Qualitative alternative talent management research in Canada	Critical HR evaluation in South Africa with a focus on diversity and inclusion	Grassroots HR development in Argentina with a focus on marginalized communities
International Business	Global market analysis in South Korea	Qualitative international business negotiations of a non-binary entrepreneur in France	Postcolonial critique of international trade in India with a focus on cultural diversity	Fair trade initiatives in Bolivia with a focus on indigenous artisans
Investments	Portfolio analysis in Russia	Qualitative investment strategies of a traditional village bread maker in China	Critical examination of investment banking in India with a focus on social responsibility	Community-based impact investing in Peru with a focus on sustainable development
Management	Performance metrics in the USA	Qualitative leadership studies of a Syrian refugee in the UK	Critical analysis of corporate power in Brazil with a focus on women's rights	Grassroots management practices in South Africa with a focus on employee empowerment
Marketing	Consumer behavior research in Egypt	Qualitative marketing campaigns of an indigenous village in Brazil	Critical analysis of marketing ethics in the USA with a focus on multiculturalism	Grassroots marketing for social causes in Kenya with a focus on community impact
Real Estate	Property market analysis in Australia	Qualitative real estate market studies of a female real estate agent in the USA	Analysis of real estate development practices in the UK with a focus on people of African heritage	Community-based affordable housing projects in Mexico

Interpretivist Paradigm. The weakness of positivist research is the strength of interpretivist research. Interpretivist research provides a deep understanding of contexts as well as the subjectivity and various viewpoints of people under examination. It depicts thick description and profound perceptions from various points of view. However, as interpretivist research is contextual, its findings far from having the power of generalizability and transferability. Rather, its conclusions are unique to a specific study.

Critical Paradigm. While positivist research asserts its neutrality, critical research is unabashed in its stance on social justice. Critical research investigates social inequalities, such as the power of men over women in all fields of endeavor in society in general. The role of critical researchers is to elevate the consciousness of readers with a view to recognize the inequalities in society: between the majority and the minority, between people of different colors, ethnicities, religions, cultures, social status, and the like. This type of research is politically charged. At times, rights of different groups clash, resulting in culture wars in identity politics.

Transformative Paradigm. The advantage of transformative research is that it not only describes the world as it is, the way positivist research does, but more importantly exposes and opposes the unbalanced power structure in a world characterized by systemic violence. Here, the researcher is engaged in action research with the people which the researcher supports. Transformative research acts in unison with most of the working people to dismantle the unjust power structures which supports the gross inequality between the very few rich and the majority poor. The merit of transformative research is that it is engaged with the grassroots community from the bottom up to solve deeply rooted problems which empowers the people in their efforts to work for social change. The shortcoming of transformative research is that the researcher is involved in complex social realities which is difficult to change. Moreover, the status quo resists acts of radical change that transformative research proposes.

CONCLUSION

Summary

Figure 4: Summary of the Contending Research Paradigms
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Who Cares?

Each research paradigm has a deeply embedded set of assumptions, for which reason researcher must know what paradigm they are using in each research work. Academicians, the business sector, civil society, decision makers, and society-at-large gain from this research, as they will have a level playing field in the understanding of the perspectives of researchers, their research outputs, and their potential impacts on specific sectors of society.

So What?

The use of each research paradigm will result in the researcher using a given methodology which produces a different conclusion. Thus, research paradigms are important, of which researchers must be aware. Positivist paradigm produces quantitative results about the status quo without disturbing it. Interpretivist paradigm produces qualitative and meaning-laden findings. Critical paradigm produces research that calls for the advocacy of social justice for certain groups. Transformative research demands radical engagements that dismantle the status quo. All four paradigms provide different lenses through which to investigate and deal with the natural world.

Now What? Recommendations

Prior to engaging in any research endeavor, researchers are enjoined to reflect on the paradigms which they will use in the conduct of their research projects. A research paradigm provides the direction through which the research work will be steered. Empowered with the understanding of the different paradigms, authors identify which research design, research methods, statistical tools, and research strategies will be best used for a given objective.

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Conclusion

This analytical paper has laid out an exhaustive panorama of different paradigms of research. It bridged the gap in the lack of knowledge of many researchers on the paradigms that undergird their research. Whatever the aim of the researcher might be, whether to identify quantitative trends, search for meaning in life, champion social justice, or dismantle unequal structures of power, there are paradigms that are best suited for specific research work. With an understanding of the diversity of research paradigms, the researchers are empowered to choose the paradigm that best fits their research agenda, thereby leading to meaningfully engage with the social phenomena, which we aim not only to comprehend but also ameliorate.

REFERENCES:

- Comte, A. (1988). *Introduction to Positive Philosophy*. Hackett Publishing Company, Inc.
- Crenshaw, K. (1996). *Critical Race Theory: The Key Writings That Formed the Movement*. The New Press.
- Geertz, C. (1973). Thick Description: Towards an Interpretive Theory of Culture. In *The Interpretation of Cultures: Selected Essays*.
- Kuhn, T. S. (2012). *The structure of scientific revolutions: 50th anniversary edition*. The University of Chicago Press.
- Marcuse, H. (2007). *One-dimensional man: Studies in the ideology of advanced industrial society* (D. Kellner, Trans.; Repr). Routledge.
- Popper, K. (2002). *The logic of scientific discovery*. Routledge.
- Rancière, J., & Swenson, J. (2011). *Mute speech: Literature, critical theory, and politics*. Columbia University Press.
- Ty, R. (2021). A participatory action research on the care for water and life on Earth: A case study of interreligious and intercultural engagements in the time of the pandemic in Thailand. *Caminhos de Diálogo*, 9(15), 156–176.
- Ty, R. (2009). Where Have All the Indigenous Peoples Gone? A Participatory Action Research: Embracing the Moment to Act in a Time of Change. *Proceedings of the 29th Annual Midwest Research-to-Practice Conference In Adult, Continuing, Community and Extension Education*.

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Ty, R., Daniels, D., C., & Pongo, T. (2010). And Justice for All! The Contributions of the African Diaspora to

the Enrichment of Critical Theory: Postcolonial Theory and Critical Race Theory. *Proceedings of*

the African American Latino/a American Leadership Conference. African American Latino/a

American Leadership Conference, DeKalb, IL.

Weber, M. (1977). *The Protestant Ethic and the Spirit of Capitalism*. Macmillan.